

A Critical Review of the G20 Economies NDCS to Meet the Paris Agreement Goals

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Abstract

Countries committed to a number of climate activities under the Paris Agreement, including post-2020 greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction objectives. The G20 economies' estimated GHG emissions under existing climate policies are compared to the GHG targets established in the nationally decided contributions in this study (NDCs). It is based on a review of official government estimates as well as independent national and international research. Six G20 members (China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Russia, and Turkey) are expected to fulfill their unconditional NDC objectives with present policy, according to the report. To meet their goals, eight members (Argentina, Australia, Canada, the European Union, Republic of Korea, South Africa, and the United States) must take further steps. Saudi Arabia has little data, while emission forecasts for Brazil and Mexico are susceptible to great uncertainty. The study also includes high-level decarbonisation indicators to help understand current progress toward meeting the NDCs; Saudi Arabia and South Africa were found to be continuing to increase both emission intensity per unit GDP and emissions per capita under current policies by 2030, compared to 2015 levels.

Keywords: Decarbonisation, Greenhouse, G20 economies', Emission

1. Introduction

Currently the Paris Agreement is in effect, nations must step up their ambition in post-2020 climate commitments to reach the Paris Agreement's goals (Höhne et al., 2017; Rogelj et al., 2016). The Paris Agreement intends to keep global warming well below 2 degrees Celsius compared to pre-industrial levels, while also pursuing measures to keep it below 1.5 degrees Celsius (UNFCCC, 2015a). Almost all nations submitted national post-2020 climate action plans and commitments as part of their Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) in preparation of the Paris meeting. The Paris Agreement is founded on these pledges. By the 15th of November 2017, 192 of the 197 UNFCCC Parties have submitted their INDCs, accounting for over 98 percent of world 2012 emissions. The agreement has been approved by over 170 countries, converting their INDCs into NDCs. While the present NDCs are expected to lower warming compared to a no-policy baseline, even if completely implemented, their cumulative mitigation impact would fall well short of what is required to keep global warming well below 2 degrees Celsius, let alone 1.5 degrees Celsius (Rogelj et al., 2016).

NDCs are not one-time or static pledges; governments must strengthen them on a recurring basis, based on progress evaluations conducted every five years under the Paris Agreement. The 2018 Facilitative Dialogue (now known as the "Talanoa Dialogue") kicks off the process, in which countries review their collective efforts toward meeting the Paris climate targets for the first time, and use the results to inform the development of NDCs. In addition to the collective assessment, the extent to which individual countries are progressing toward achieving their NDCs/INDCs (hereafter referred to as NDCs, unless a country that has not ratified the Paris Agreement is mentioned) is also relevant to the preparation of future NDCs, because countries on track to meet or exceed their current commitments may be particularly well positioned to take on stronger commitments.

A uniform and harmonised approach to tracking countries' progress toward their NDCs at various levels of detail and from various viewpoints is also becoming increasingly important. Compston and Bailey (2016), Höhne et al. (2018), and Peters et al. (2017) have all presented several assessment indicators and frameworks in recent years.

This document provides an updated evaluation of the emissions associated with each G20 member's NDC targets and existing policies. Due to the G20 economies are responsible for around three-quarters of the global GHG emissions, their ability to implement (or surpass) their NDCs will have a significant impact on the Paris Agreement's goals. So far, no peer-reviewed literature has evaluated the progress of all G20 economies toward their NDC pledges in a consistent manner. Assessments made under the UNFCCC can be supplemented with independent, comparable analyses.

This study builds on the work done for the 2017 UNEP Emissions Gap Report (UNEP, 2017) by updating emissions projections for the current policy scenario from recently published National Communications and Third Biennial Reports for seven G20 members (Argentina, Australia, Canada, EU28, Japan, Russia, and Turkey) (UNFCCC, 2018b, 2018d), as well as new and/or updated country-specific studies for seven G20 members (national models), and four global model studies. This study also compares NDCs and current policy scenario projections by looking at commonly used high-level decarbonisation indicators to provide additional insights into the G20 members' progress toward the NDC targets (Section 2) and describe the detailed methodology underlying the analysis (Section 3).

Methodology

2.1 NDC scenario (unconditional and conditional)

NDC scenario identifies the GHG emissions that each member could emit in the target year (2025 for the US, 2030 for the rest of the G20) under unconditional and conditional NDCs. Emission levels reported by national governments are used as central estimates where available (UNFCCC, 2016); alternatively, emission levels are calculated using base-year or baseline data based on NDCs and other official documents submitted by countries to the UNFCCC (e.g. national GHG inventories, national communications, biennial reports, and biennial update reports). If official figures are unavailable, estimations of emission levels published in the literature are taken into account.

2.2 Current policy scenario (independent studies)

This scenario estimates emissions for the target year, taking into consideration emission projections arising from the full implementation of current policies, as determined by independent studies. The emissions forecasts examined here encompass major energy and climate policies that were in place by a recent cut-off date (i.e., 2016 or 2017 depending on the research) and do not include future policies that were still being considered or planned at the time of the cut-off date. Furthermore, while studies differ in their approaches to quantifying policy impact, they do not assume that policy targets will be met simply because they are enshrined in the form of a law or a strategy document – studies also take into account the status of policy implementation and the extent to which the policy plan is backed up by measures. The Climate Action Tracker (CAT, 2018a), the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2017), the Joint Research Centre (JRC) (Kitous et al., 2017), and the PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency all provided estimates (Kuramochi et al., 2017a; PBL, 2017; den Elzen et al., 2016). We also looked at estimates from a variety of country-specific sources that were based on national models. By providing data that aims for consistency between countries and political independence, the independent study of current policy trajectories complements the official sources indicated.

2.3 NDC targets evaluation

We analyzed whether G20 members are on track to reach their NDC targets based on other studies emissions data collected. The following categories of evaluation were established:

I On track,

(ii) Additional activity required, and

(iii) Incomplete or erroneous information.

The review did not take into account the possibility of using offsets to meet the emission reduction targets; instead, it looked at national emission patterns.

Based on the quantity of independent research that supports each of the evaluation categories, we first determined whether a country would fall into the first two groups. We also looked at the average estimates of the current policy scenario projections across all studies when the studies were ambiguous or showed significant ranges (median estimates are used when more than five studies are available). The second evaluation category ('further action needed') was split into two subcategories: 'low additional effort,' which denoted a current policy trajectory (average estimate across studies) less than 15% lower than the (average) unconditional NDC target, and 'high additional effort,' which denoted a current policy trajectory (average) more than 15% higher than the unconditional NDC target. When studies disagreed significantly on their present policy scenario estimates or there was insufficient evidence to measure countries' progress toward their NDC targets, the third evaluation category ('uncertain or insufficient information') was used.

2.4 Decarbonisation indicators assessment

A variety of high-level decarbonisation indicators that are often utilized in the context of climate policy making were used to assess the quantified emissions range for NDC targets and current policy scenario forecasts.

The findings of the examination to see if G20 members are on track to reach their unconditional NDCs. Three crucial caveats should be kept in mind when reading this section. To begin with, not all NDCs need the same amount of effort to implement, so a country that is on schedule to meet its NDCs is taking more mitigating action than one that is not. It is greatly dependent on the amount of ambition of the NDCs, which this study does not measure, as well as the strength of the current policy settings. Second, these estimates are subject to the uncertainty that comes with macroeconomic trends like GDP and population growth, as well as technological advancements and policy impacts. Section 6 delves more into the methodology's cautions and limitations.

Starting with the four highest-emitting economies, China, the EU28, India, and the United States, the next section delves deeper into each of the G20 nations.

China's NDC has three major mitigation goals: (1) peak CO₂ emissions around 2030, with best efforts to peak earlier; (2) lower the carbon intensity of its GDP by 60–65 percent from 2005 levels by 2030; and (3) attain a 20% non-fossil fuel share in primary energy consumption by 2030. Only energy-related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are addressed by these goals. China also promises to expand forest stock volume by 4.5 billion m³ by 2030, compared to 2005 levels. There is no official estimate of 2030 emissions related with the NDC targets. However, the National Center for Climate Change Strategy and International Cooperation (NCSC) (Sha, 2018; Sha et al., 2017) and the Energy Research Institute (ERI) also have national figures for CO₂ emissions from the energy sector (including cement) (updated calculations based on Jiang et al., 2013). To construct GHG emission

forecasts, these were combined with historical non-CO₂ GHG emissions (The People's Republic of China, 2017) and non-CO₂ emission growth rates (Tavoni et al., 2015). Independent studies (CAT, 2018a; IEA, 2017; Kuramochi et al., 2017a) used China's 13th Five-Year Plan (FYP) and 13th FYP for Renewable Development to estimate China's emissions under national policies (including renewable capacity targets and a cap on coal consumption). Although there are a wide variety of emission forecasts, these analyses imply that China's 2030 emissions will be lower than those projected from complete implementation of the NDC targets. Total GHG emissions are expected to continue to rise until 2030, though at a slower rate than in the past (2000–2012), according to Jiang et al. analysis (2017). Many of the research included in this report have revised their projections downward from previous estimates, but only a few studies suggest that CO₂ emissions will peak before 2030 (Climate Action Tracker – lower end; Green and Stern, 2017). In 2012, China began to limit coal use and increase clean energy use as a result of air pollution management laws (State Council, 2013). This, combined with structural changes, such as rebalancing the economy away from heavy industries and toward services, led in a slowdown in most energy-intensive manufacturing, a peak in coal use in 2013, and a continuous fall in coal usage from 2014. More than 120 GW of new installed wind, solar, and hydropower capacity has been added in the last two years. However, coal use surged in 2017, reversing some of the declines seen since 2013 (Le Quere et al., 2017), and energy-related CO₂ emissions are anticipated to have reached a new all-time high in 2017 (IEA, 2018).

The EU28's NDC includes a promise to reduce domestic emissions by at least 40% by 2030 compared to 1990. Kuramochi et al. (2017a), JRC (Kitous et al., 2017), EEA Trends report (European Environment Agency, 2017), EU Reference Scenario 2016 (European Commission, 2016b), E3MLab and IIASA (2018), Fragkos et al. (2017), and Seventh National Communication (European Commission, 2017) all suggest that the EU28 will miss its NDC target under current policies. E3MLab and IIASA (2018), as well as Fragkos et al. (2017), created policy scenarios based on the EU Reference Scenario 2016 and aimed at achieving the 2030 Climate & Energy Framework2 targets (NDC target, binding renewable target, energy efficiency target).

The EU Emission Trading System (EU ETS), an EU-wide cap-and-trade system covering electricity generation, energy-intensive industry, and aviation, is divided into two categories: (1) policies targeting non-ETS sectors, such as transportation, agriculture, and buildings, and (2) policies targeting ETS sectors, such as transportation, agriculture, and buildings, including Member State-specific emission reduction targets captured by the Effort Sharing Decision (2013–2020). For the period 2021–2030, both policy pillars must be strengthened in order to meet the NDC target. The EU is currently debating whether to approve a big package of measures (Clean Energy for All Europeans³) aimed at accelerating GHG emission reductions in many areas. Because these policies have not yet been implemented by the European Council, their impact is not included in the analysis of the research cited above. In March 2018, the EU ETS was revised for the period 2021 to 2030, with three key elements: reducing the cap at a 2.2 percent annual rate from 2021 onwards; doubling the Market Stability Reserve (MSR) feeding rate between 2019 and 2023 to reduce allowance surpluses; and invalidating allowances in the MSR exceeding the number of allowances auctioned the previous year, from 2023 onwards (Council of the European Union, 2017b). This legally enforceable cap contributes to the ETS sector's targeted 2030 reductions (a 43 percent reduction from 2005). European Commission, 2015) In May 2018, the provisionally agreed Effort Sharing Regulation was established, which applies to GHG emissions from sectors not covered by the EU ETS, such as transportation, buildings, agriculture, and waste management. The overall aim for these sectors is a 30% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, compared to 2005, which will be achieved through legally enforceable yearly emission limits for each Member State for the years 2021–2030. (Council of the European Union, 2017c; European Commission, 2016b). There's also an adopted regulation (European Parliament 2018) to incorporate GHG emissions and removals from land use, land use change, and forestry (LULUCF) into the 2030 climate and energy framework, as well as an adopted proposal to amend the Energy

Efficiency Directive and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Council of the European Union, 2017a; European Commission, 2016a). The Energy Union Governance Regulation was adopted in 2018, and it establishes interim goals for achieving the 2030 goals of 32% renewable energy and 32.5 percent energy savings. If these revised targets are satisfied, the European Commission estimates that emissions will be 40% lower in 2030 than they were in 1990.

By 2030, **India's** NDC aims to reduce its emissions intensity of GDP, excluding agriculture, by 33–35 percent below 2005 levels, increase the share of non-fossil energy in total power generation capacity to 40% (with the help of technology transfer and low-cost international finance), and create an additional cumulative carbon sink of 2.5–3 GtCO_{2e} through increased forest and tree cover. The market-based Perform, Achieve, and Trade (PAT) scheme for energy efficiency initiatives in energy-intensive sectors of the economy, renewable energy capacity targets, Clean Environment Cess (coal tax), and a range of support schemes laid out under the 12th Five Year Plan are the main mitigation-related policies implemented in India. The "unconditional" NDC predictions in Fig. 1 assume either existing policies or merely the intensity target, but the "conditional" NDC projections assume full implementation of the NDC targets, including the non-fossil fuel target. Independent studies (CAT, 2018a; Dubash et al., 2018; IEA, 2017; Mitra et al., 2017; PBL, 2017; Vishwanathan and Garg, 2017) predict that India will reduce emissions further than required by the intensity target with current policies, but it is unclear what emission level would be achieved if all three targets were combined, partly because emission projections are heavily dependent on future economic growth (e.g. Dubash et al., 2018). The National Electricity Plan was issued in 2018 (CEA, 2018). While 48.3 GW of end-of-life plants are anticipated to close by 2022, another 94.3 GW is expected to be added by 2027, according to the NEP. However, there is a chance that part of this capacity may become stranded assets.

The National Electricity Plan's estimates are in sharp contrast to the draft version (Central Electricity Authority, 2016), which predicted that no new coal-fired power capacity will be required between 2022 and 2027, following a capacity expansion of about 50 GW between 2017 and 2022.

In 2016, **the US** announced a Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to cut GHG emissions by 26–28 percent below 2005 levels by 2025. According to independent analyses (Table 1), the United States is not on pace to reach the 2025 NDC objectives under current policy (excluding the Clean Power Plan). President Donald Trump said in June 2017 that the United States will withdraw from the Paris Agreement and stop implementing the NDC. The United States informed the UN Secretary General on August 4th, 2017 that it plans to "exercise its right to withdraw" from the Paris Agreement. The earliest the United States may leave is in 2020, four years after the Paris Agreement became effective. Although the Trump Administration has said that the objective would not be adopted at the federal level, the US NDC remains legal until that time. Fransen and Levin (2017) looked at seven studies (Chai et al., 2017; Climate Action Tracker, 2017; Climate Advisers, 2017; ClimateInteractive, 2017; Hafstead, 2017; Rhodium Group, 2017a; b) and found that emissions will range from 5.6 to 6.8 GtCO_{2e}/year in 2025 under the new Administration's policies, compared to 5.0–6.6 GtCO_{2e}/year under the previous Administration's policies. In all of these scenarios, emissions in 2025 are greater than the United States' aim. These forecasts, however, are largely dependent on how soon policies are overturned or amended, as well as what policies are replaced. In addition, numerous governments, towns, and businesses have risen to the occasion in reaction to Trump's pronouncement on the Paris Deal, committing to support the agreement and take climate-change action. However, the added influence of these subnational and non-state actors' actions may offset some of the new Administration's goals (Data Driven Yale, NewClimate Institute, PBL, 2018; Kuramochi et al., 2017b).

In comparison to its INDC, **Argentina** announced a revised and more ambitious NDC (Government of Argentina, 2016). This revised NDC contains an unconditional absolute emissions target of 483 MtCO₂e/year by 2030, as well as a conditional target of 369 MtCO₂e/year by 2030, both of which include emissions from land use change and forestry (LULUCF). The revised NDC's reduced emission forecasts are partially attributable to better methodology for measuring historical emissions data in the land use sector. According to the Climate Action Tracker (CAT, 2018a), emissions predictions would still rise by roughly 50% over 2010 levels under existing policies, and Argentina would need to take additional mitigation measures to fulfill its updated NDC objectives.

Australia has pledged to reduce GHG emissions by 26–28 percent below 2005 levels by 2030, including LULUCF. According to official projections, emissions will reach 570 MtCO₂e/year in 2030 (Australian Government, 2017), compared to the NDC projections of 429–440 MtCO₂e/year. Independent assessments (CAT, 2018a; Kitous et al., 2017; Kuramochi et al., 2017a; Reputex, 2016) demonstrate that Australia's emissions will fall short of its NDC objectives for 2030 under existing policy. The Emissions Reduction Fund and related safeguard measures, which the Australian government deems a significant policy initiative, and the National Energy Productivity Plan, which seeks to increase energy productivity by 40% by 2030, are two of the most important programs.

Brazil has set an absolute emissions target of 1.3 GtCO₂e/year by 2025 and an indicative target of 1.2 GtCO₂e/year by 2030, which are 37 and 43 percent lower than 2005 emissions levels, respectively. The forest sectors, as well as expanding the amount of biofuels and renewable power in Brazil's energy mix, are among the actions being taken to meet the objectives. Two independent studies (PBL and JRC) suggest that if all implemented policies succeed (including the enforcement of the Brazilian Forest Code, biofuel policy updates, and renewable power capacity targets), emission projections will likely be in line with the NDC targets; however, two other studies (PBL and JRC) suggest that if all implemented policies succeed (including the enforcement of the Brazilian Forest Code, biofuel policy updates, and renewable power capacity targets), emission projections will likely be in line with the NDC targets.

(CAT, 2018a; Rochedo et al., 2018) anticipate increased emissions and indicate the reverse, taking into consideration the recent reversal in progress toward halting deforestation. The future of emissions is still a source of uncertainty. For example, successful policies in the LULUCF sector, such as the enforcement of the Brazilian Forest Code and efforts to reduce deforestation in the Amazon and Cerrado regions, reduced LULUCF emissions by 86 percent between 2005 and 2012 (Ministry of Science and Technology of Brazil, 2016), but recent data and analyses suggest that the decreasing trend in deforestation has slowed or even stopped (SEEG, 2017). Indeed, the country's recent political turmoil has prompted the government to surrender environmental policy reversals in return for political support, which might result in increased deforestation emissions (Rochedo et al., 2018).

By 2030, **Canada's** NDC pledges to a 30% decrease in emissions from 2005 levels. According to government forecasts, emissions will exceed 742 MtCO₂e/year by 2030, compared to a goal of 523 MtCO₂e/year (excluding LULUCF) (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2017). A fuel efficiency criterion for passenger vehicles and a carbon standard for newly constructed coal-fired power plants are the two key measures now in place. According to independent research, Canada is far from meeting its NDC target under present policy. Canada recently announced a proposal to price carbon emissions that would compel individual provinces to either impose a direct carbon price or implement a cap-and-trade system. The analysis did not take into account this intended policy.

Indonesia's NDC contains a target of 29 percent below BAU without condition and a conditional target of 41 percent below BAU with appropriate international cooperation by 2030, both of which include LULUCF. Due to deforestation, peat land degradation, and land-use change, the LULUCF sector accounts for a major portion of Indonesia's emissions. GHG emissions from LULUCF are predicted to rise over time, owing to the continuous growth of large-scale oil palm plantations, however the emission forecasts are subject to significant uncertainty. According to the independent studies shown in Table 1, Indonesia is on course to meet its unconditional NDC, with total GHG emissions increasing since 2010.

Japan's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) targets to cut GHG emissions by 26% below 2013 levels by 2030. According to recent independent evaluations, Japan is on pace to reach its NDC with existing policy (such as the renewable feed-in tariff scheme and the 2014 Basic Energy Plan). The NDC also establishes a target for electricity generating mix, with 26 percent coal, 27 percent gas, 20–22 percent nuclear, and 22–24 percent renewables. However, there is still a significant lot of ambiguity about nuclear and coal power's future roles, as it is unclear when and by which energy carrier's nuclear capacity will be replaced.

Mexico's NDC intends to cut GHG emissions by 22 percent (unconditional) to 36 percent (conditional) by 2030 compared to BAU. By 2024, Mexico wants to generate 35 percent of its electricity from sustainable energy sources⁵. Mexico's new Energy Transition Law lays out broad policies and objectives for renewable energy, energy efficiency, and greenhouse gas reductions (Government of Mexico, 2015).

Mexico is on pace to fulfill the unconditional NDC objective under present policies, but more mitigation activities are required to meet the conditional NDC target (Kuramochi et al., 2017a).

In its NDC, **the Republic of Korea** pledged to cut GHG emissions by 37 percent below BAU by 2030. According to recent independent studies, existing policies would cause emissions to surpass the NDC emission threshold. Renewable energy objectives for 2020 and 2030, as well as the national carbon trading scheme, are the main current measures under consideration (ETS). In 2016, the Roadmap to Achieve the National GHG Reduction Target for 2030 was released, detailing emissions predictions, reduction goals, and significant emission reduction programs for eight sectors (The Government of the Republic of Korea, 2017). The new administration, which gained power in May 2017, announced intentions to adopt new policies aimed at increasing renewable energy and reducing dependency on coal. Following that, a new 15-year "Power Supply and Demand Plan" was announced, confirming the plan to move electricity generation away from coal and nuclear and toward renewables (CAT, 2018b; Ministry of Trade Industry and Energy, 2018). According to CAT (2018a), such initiatives might help the Republic of Korea go closer to fulfilling its NDC.

By 2030, **Russia's** NDC seeks to reduce GHG emissions to 70–75 percent of 1990 levels. Independent estimates of the INDC emission level varied greatly, owing mostly to differing interpretations of LULUCF emissions accounting. Under present policy, emission levels in 2030 are expected to be below the lower end of Russia's INDC range.

Through measures and strategies that also contribute to economic diversification and adaptation, **Saudi Arabia's** NDC intends to achieve yearly emission reductions of up to 130 MtCO_{2e} by 2030. The country has not yet identified a baseline, according to the NDC, which will be calculated based on weighted combinations of two scenarios that differ in terms of their expectations about how oil would be allocated: for local consumption or export. Saudi Arabia is not on pace to fulfill its NDC objective, according to independent assessments (JRC and CAT). We conclude that it is impossible to tell whether Saudi Arabia is on track given the uncertainty surrounding the NDC objective and the paucity of data available.

The NDC for **South Africa** includes a 'peak, plateau, and decrease' GHG emissions trajectory, with a range of 398–614 MtCO₂e/year between 2025 and 2030, with a peak between 2020 and 2025 and a plateau for the following decade before starting to fall. The Integrated Resource Plan for Electricity, which is the most important policy impacting South Africa's GHG emissions, is included in the current policies projection. South Africa's GHG emissions, according to all analyses, are 50 MtCO₂e/year to over 400 MtCO₂e/year above the NDC emissions range under existing policy.

Turkey's INDC proposes a decrease in GHG emissions of up to 21% below BAU by 2030 (about 900 MtCO₂e/year). Renewable energy objectives are included in the current policy projections. Independent analyses reveal that emissions forecasts range from 525 to 1000 MtCO₂e/year. This wide range suggests that the INDC might be easily met (based on PBL and JRC emissions predictions under present policy) or projected to be met (based on government estimates reflected in the projection of CAT, 2018a).

Results and Discussions

3.1 Understanding the required reduction efforts of the G20 members collectively

According to our findings, the G20 nations' present policies fall short of reaching the unconditional NDCs. To meet all of the unconditional NDCs, G20 economies would likely need to implement additional measures to decrease 2030 GHG emissions by roughly 2.5 GtCO₂e, and by about 3.5 GtCO₂e to meet all of the conditional NDCs.

Additional work is needed, according to study, and the largest contributions would need to come from Australia, Canada, the Republic of Korea, South Africa, and the United States in particular. In terms of extra reduction efforts as a proportion of existing policy estimates, these four nations have the most (between 20 percent and 25 percent). For the United States, linear interpolation between the NDC target year (2025) and the 2050 long-term target (83 percent reduction below 2005 levels) was assumed to estimate the 2030 target—it should be noted that the required additional emissions reductions would be halved if the 2030 target remained at the same level as for 2025, rather than progressing linearly towards its 2050 target as assumed in our analysis (and many studies assessed in Rogelj et al. (2016) and UNFCCC).

Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 2, the emission targets of three NDCs (India, Russia, and Turkey) are predicted to be higher than the estimated present policy scenario levels. As a result of their existing policies, these nations are anticipated to exceed their NDC objectives by around 1 GtCO₂e. We have assumed that this overachievement compensates the underachievement of other objectives for the gap listed above, and that these nations would continue on their existing policy paths rather than the ones predicted by their NDCs. We also compared 2030 G20 emissions under existing policies and NDCs to those based on 2°C scenarios. The G20's 2030 emissions levels for the 2°C pathways are based on the total greenhouse gas emissions levels of all individual G20 members predicted (median estimate) by 450 ppm CO₂e scenarios (van Soest et al., 2017). The delayed 450 ppm CO₂e scenarios are based on global emission scenarios from Integrated Assessment Models from various projects, such as AMPERE (Kriegler et al., 2015; Riahi et al., 2015) and LIMITS (Tavoni et al., 2015), which assume limited action until 2020 and global least-cost emission reduction pathways starting from 2020, and are consistent with a greater than 66 percent chance of keeping global warming below 2 °C. The G20 emission levels for 2°C pathways in 2030 are anticipated to be 27 (range: 23–31) GtCO₂e (about 20% below 2010 levels), which is around 13.5 GtCO₂e lower than the median projection for existing policies (about 40.5 GtCO₂e, or 8 percent above 2010 levels).

Based on the amount of research that supports each of the evaluation categories, we conclude that a country I is on track or (ii) requires additional action. Recent analyses imply that, based on these parameters, China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Russia, and Turkey are on track to meet or exceed their unconditional NDC targets with the current degree of uncertainty. According to the UN, Argentina, Australia, Canada, the EU28, South Africa, the Republic of Korea, and the United States need to take more steps to fulfill their NDCs.

3.2 Understanding the mitigation efforts of the NDCs

The preceding sections looked at whether G20 members needed to enact additional measures, both individually and collectively, to reach their NDC objectives. This section provides high-level decarbonisation metrics to help you better understand how the G20 economies are progressing toward their NDCs. This is accomplished by analyzing changes in these metrics during 2010, as well as decoupling emissions in terms of population and GDP using a few measures presented in the literature (Peters et al., 2017). We make no attempt to convey the NDC objectives' level of ambition. In order to determine whether the magnitude of change in GHG emission-related indicators as a result of NDCs is ambitious and fair in light of the Paris Agreement's long-term goal, explicit benchmarking across alternative normative indicators of effort sharing is required, which is beyond the scope of this research.. However, a number of recent peer-reviewed studies (CAT, 2018a; Hohne et al., 2018; Pan et al., 2017; Robiou du Pont et al., 2017) have attempted this task using a variety of effort sharing allocations based on different equity principles (CAT, 2018a; Hohne et al., 2018; Pan et al., 2017; Robiou du Pont et al., 2017). (Hohne et al., 2014).

In light of the findings of this study, a nation that is on pace to fulfill its NDC does not necessarily imply that it will implement more strict mitigation measures than a country that is not. There are three major causes behind this.

First, the ambition levels of the NDC objectives vary. A nation that is not on pace to reach its NDC objective may have set a very ambitious goal for itself, whereas a country that is on track to accomplish its goal may have set a relatively modest goal. A number of recent studies have examined the NDC objectives' ambition and fairness using a variety of effort-sharing ratios based on various criteria and equity principles (CAT, 2018a; Hohne et al., 2018; Pan et al., 2017; Robiou du Pont et al., 2017). Furthermore, because NDCs are made at the national level and are varied in character, comparing progress across nations is not always easy.

Second, the current policy scenario forecasts reported in this study only account for existing policies until 2016, therefore our findings should not be construed as a prediction of whether nations will fulfill their NDC objectives. Countries have only had three years to design their NDCs. If governments vowed more than they would have accomplished anyhow, a gap between mitigation objectives and existing policy trajectories is not surprising. The difference may narrow in the coming years as countries enact new policies and improve the execution of existing ones.

Third, various countries have diverse methods to policymaking. Some governments use promises or objectives to motivate more ambitious policies, while others just use them to formalize the intended impact of existing policies.

Conclusions and policy implications

The progress of the G20 nations achieving the greenhouse emission objectives established in their nationally determined contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement was examined in this article. According to the analysis, NDC implementation will result in lower emissions than the existing policy scenario for many G20

economies, implying that additional policies will be required to fulfill the NDC target (barring the use of offsets or unpredicted macroeconomic shifts, as mentioned above). The NDC target emission levels for other nations were found to be higher than existing policy scenario forecasts. (We do not analyze the NDC objectives' ambition levels; this may be done by applying various equity-based effort sharing methodologies to global emission paths consistent with attaining 2 or 1.5 degrees Celsius.)

We reach the following findings after carefully considering the cautions and limitations indicated in Section 6. In all, recent studies reviewed here imply that under present policy, six G20 nations (China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Russia, and Turkey) are on pace to meet or exceed their unconditional 2030 commitments. Because future emission forecasts are uncertain, determining whether Brazil, Mexico, and Saudi Arabia are on pace to fulfill their NDCs is challenging. To fully track growth, better data and more national studies are required. The number of studies examining whether nations are on pace to meet their NDC objectives is currently limited in the literature, despite the fact that the implementation of the NDCs is becoming increasingly relevant from a policy standpoint.

According to government and independent estimates, the seven remaining G20 economies (Argentina, Australia, Canada, EU28, South Africa, Republic of Korea, and the United States) need to adopt enhanced and new climate and energy policies because their projected reductions by the target year fall short of the reductions targeted in their NDCs. These policies could focus on further decarbonisation of energy supply and energy efficiency (for example, increasing energy efficiency in industry, buildings, and transportation, increasing investments in renewable energy technologies, and reducing coal use), as well as non-energy sector mitigation (such as afforestation, reducing methane emissions arising from oil and gas production and reducing hydro fluorocarbon or HFC emissions).

Many nations (including G20 economies) have already effectively implemented a wide variety of climate and energy policies to minimize greenhouse gas emissions (such as renewable energy, efficiency requirements in transportation and appliances, and afforestation and reforestation) (e.g., Fekete et al., 2015; Roelfsema et al., 2018). G20 economies might adopt or improve these measures, if appropriate, because they have previously shown to be effective at a low cost. This would assist them in meeting or exceeding their present obligations.

Some of the economies that are not on pace based on our findings are preparing to adopt new policies (such as the EU28's ETS reform and the Republic of Korea's Plan for Electricity Supply and Demand), which, once implemented, will cut future emissions even more.

The G20 economies' progress in lowering GHG emissions relative to previous levels differs as well. Current measures are expected to have an influence on emissions, but they will not prevent emissions from increasing through 2030. In many G20 economies, this is the case (Argentina, Australia, China, India, Mexico, Republic of Korea, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and Turkey). Under existing policy, emissions in the other G20 economies are expected to stay steady, or even decline, at present levels.

The per capita emission forecasts under present policies likewise reveal a broad variance across G20 nations, with Saudi Arabia, Australia, Argentina, the United States, and Canada having the highest per capita emissions in 2030. With the exception of Saudi Arabia and South Africa, and to a lesser extent Russia, many G20 economies have a decoupling of economic growth and greenhouse gas emissions under existing policy.

With certain exceptions, inequalities in per capita emissions and emission intensity are beginning to narrow, but they remain substantially above the global average level required to meet the Paris Agreement temperature objectives of 1.5 °C or 2 °C.

For the Paris Agreement's climate goals to be met, G20 economies must adopt enhanced and new policies that go beyond current NDC targets, so that their combined mitigation effect leads to global emission levels that are needed to keep global warming well below 2 degrees Celsius, if not below 1.5 degrees Celsius. Subnational actors, such as towns and regional governments, may take further action, while non-state entities may also assist in exceeding NDC targets.

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